

Modern Mystery School (MMS)

also known as "Rocky Mountain Mystery School"

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Entry tags: Spiritual Business, Mystery Religion, New Age Religion, Religious Group

Modern Mystery School (MMS), formerly known as the Rocky Mountain Mystery School (RMMS), is variously described as a spiritual path, a spiritual business, and a spiritual lineage. It was founded in 1997 by Gudni Gudnason and is headquartered in Toronto and Tokyo. MMS emerged in Japan at the height of the 'spirituality boom' and the proliferation of spiritual therapeutic techniques that are often associated with the eclectic categories of Western esotericism or New Age. MMS teaches that there are seven Mystery Schools in the world where esoteric knowledge is transmitted in a continuous lineage for thousands of years. While these Mystery Schools are closed and shrouded in secrecy, MMS advertises "no more secrets" and provides open initiation through an ascending spiritual syllabus. The course material is remarkably ecumenical, drawing from Kabbalah, Theosophy, Wicca, Mikkyo, Tibetan Buddhism, Christianity, ancient Egyptian cosmologies, Norse mythology, Tarot and Reiki (among others). Tibetan ritual objects (purbha) and concepts (Shambhala) are central to ritual practice and MMS eschatology, as are ritual swords based on knighthood from European classical antiquity. Workshops and seminars are offered at both MMS headquarters and in hundreds of spiritual salons (saron). Upon completion of one of seven initiatory steps (Adept, Healer, Ritual Master 1, 2, 2.5, and 3, culminating with Guide), initiates are awarded certifications and are empowered by MMS to practice and teach specific modalities. This system of spiritual credentialism, which allows students to become teachers (called Healers or Guides) who enlist their own paying clients, complicates traditional ideas of 'the religious' and blurs the distinction between belief and business. For more recent theorization of the exchanges of spirituality and materiality, see BBB under 'Online Sources'. There is an ongoing debate, playing out on social media, traditional print media, and various online forums, about the business model of MMS (see 'Online Sources' for a sample). MMS teachings are diverse and have flexible canonicity based on Mr. Gudnason revealing new modalities and making eschatological prophesies. There is no formal canon of scripture, although the Hermetica and Kabbalah are central. 'The Cherubim's Flames' is a booklet of ritual incantations and mantras published by MMS and used by initiates. MMS primarily gives oral teachings, available in seminars, following in the tradition of the Mystery School for thousands of years, as described by Mr. Gudnason. Prominent teachings include both the universal realization of humanity's oneness as Galactic Beings and the self-realization of our own individuality. Through guided workshops with a focus on aesthetics, self-branding and self-based leadership (Knowing Thyself), initiates (especially in Japan) are encouraged to increasingly individualize: to discover their unique "channeling contract" with a specific deity (the Channeling School is only available in Japan); to be given a personalized Ritual Master name by a lineage Ipsissimus during the 2nd-step Ritual Master initiation ceremony that speaks to their unique mission on Earth; and to "find joy" through reconnecting with sources of daily pleasure. Guides are encouraged to embrace the "Royal Life" by discovering their unique embodiment of divinity and their truest self-presentation. This can include beautifying interior designs of homes and spiritual salons, an overall material upgrade in the quality of life, and fashion makeovers (Mr. Gudnason practices "Sacred Dandyism"; Mrs. Gudnason has a fashion brand; and several Japanese Guides actively promote their physical self-transformation as an aspect of Being Royal through the NEW LIFE online magazine). Initiates are also encouraged to realize their cosmic significance as part of En-sof ("The Divine Light") in spreading Light, combating Darkness, and helping to usher in the future of balance, peace and harmony (Shambhala). MMS social organization includes Founder Gudni, whose Sacred Dandy style and extraordinary (and extraterrestrial) biographical claims might be thought of as close to Weberian charismatic authority; Hideto Nakagome and Dave Lanyon—all "Third Order Ipsissimuses" with specialized regional and theological roles; the "Council of 12" women, six from the West and six from the East, who "execute the directives of the Hierarchy of Light" and are deeply involved with the interworking of MMS; high-level leadership who perform various roles (Grand Oracle, secretary, accountant and producers, among others often working in pairs or groups) and provide marketing/business tips to Guides; hundreds of certified Healers and Guides who may operate their own spiritual salons; and thousands of Adepts, low-level initiates and followers who may receive counseling at MMS salons or attend workshops at the headquarters. Japanese students are overwhelmingly female and often participating in the spiritual marketplace seeking community, self-transformation, healing from specific forms of trauma, and an enlarged sense of self amidst patriarchal social expectations. The data collected for this entry comes from ongoing fieldwork in Tokyo, beginning in May 2021, including attending seminars and interviewing Healers, Guides and two of the three Third Order Ipsissimuses (Gudni Gudnason and Hideto Nakagome). All interviewees gave consent for the use of data in academic publications.

Date Range: 1997 CE - 2021 CE

Region: Primarily North America and Japan

Region tags: United States, Japan, Brazil, Canada, South Africa, South Korea, United Kingdom

The two main headquarters are in Tokyo and Toronto. Besides Japan and Canada, substantial followers are in the USA, South Africa, UK, Brazil, and South Korea.

Status of Participants:

Elite Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: <https://www.modernmysteryschoolint.com/>

— Source 2: <https://www.facebook.com/modernmysteryschool/>

– Source 3: <https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/30874216/4208-with-cover-page-v2.pdf?Expires=1629717089&Signature=Q-b0AQYDzkAfe3wte3z4tuePXSH0Pkm-TFYbGgUUfJHoxsnS9SWJWnXOe8P1JaGBRE8pPAO4H-b65q4wz-eyjfnKjb852HaloFgPaFpcNZYI365MzkUYXfVcB0chFK-ARjINBvyPPoOY3smB5CrkUjSnXTeya8q4e7yd22MJLbaHDEjrRhpvGP5SV3vLroTwRN9D08MYIE9mRLBQhtfyOFz7d15XcPCzKBSavBBC9TQZKZAVKPair-Id=APKAJLOHF5GCSLRBV4ZA>

Notes: Source 1: A primary international website for English-speaking Western initiates. Source 2: Main MMS Facebook Page Source 3: Academic article by Ioannis Gaitanidis about the credentialization of spiritual therapies in Japan, encompassing MMS.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://eikosworld.com/en/>
- Source 1 Description: Eiko is Gudni's wife and a member of the Council of 12. She specializes in fashion, design and spiritual beauty. She teaches the Be Royal seminar and has taught the Passion School (about eroticism) in the past.
- Source 2 URL: <https://modernmysteryschoolnorcal.com/modern-mystery-school>
- Source 2 Description: Provides a clear graphic on the MMS syllabus from Adept to Guide.
- Source 3 URL: <https://centerforcontemporarybuddhiststudies.wordpress.com/bbb-project/>
- Source 3 Description: Although about Buddhism and not MMS, the BBB research cluster at the University of Copenhagen investigates the relationship between value and religion in a way that helps to understand some MMS dynamics.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.vice.com/en/article/k78ay3/inside-the-bizarre-cult-whose-members-allege-sexual-and-financial-exploitation>
- Source 1 Description: The most mainstream publication about MMS, which draws from interviews with some former MMS members and highlights various accusations.
- Source 2 URL: <https://dialogueireland.wordpress.com/2017/11/16/the-truth-about-the-modern-mystery-school/>
- Source 2 Description: An anti-cult website run by Mike Garde, a Mennonite theologian. There are dozens of pages of threads, mostly critical of MMS. Dialogue Ireland is a non-profit that exposes 'cultism' and includes lengthy attacks on the Dalai Lama and allegations of sexual perversions among 'Tibetan Lamaists'.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.modernmysteryschoolint.com/international-articles/truth-modern-mystery-school-cult-community-lightworkers/>
- Source 3 Description: A rebuttal from MMS International about cult allegations.
- Source 1 URL: <http://www.alchemyconference.net/2011/2011-Speakers.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: Source 1: 2011 International Alchemy Conference
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZGUKFztcUPY&t=19s>
- Source 2 Description: Interview with Gudni Gudnason on Jordan Bain's Unveiling Podcast
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vgbTfj5T2J8>
- Source 3 Description: Gudni Gudnason explaining concept of lineage

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: https://books.google.co.jp/books?hl=en&lr=&id=kQYAFo0Cn78C&oi=fnd&pg=PT7&dq=alice+bailey+theosophy&ots=42YRI_Ue5R&sig=xbo-EI3doYZWgcS9kGBvKJHLWnk&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=alice%20bailey%20theosophy&f=false
- Source 1 Description: Alice Bailey's "The Externalisation of the Hierarchy" -- a Theosophical touchstone that gives insight into MMS teachings about intergalactic energy, the coming Shambhala, and focus on Tibetan mysticism.
- Source 2 URL: https://books.google.co.jp/books/about/Hermetica.html?id=OVZP6b9cqLkC&redir_esc=y
- Source 2 Description: "The Hermetica" -- central to understanding the mystical Platonism of MMS teachings.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781315745916-29/hermetic-order-golden-dawn-robert-gilbert>
- Source 3 Description: "Hermetic Order of the Golden Dawn" -- providing background into the esoteric training Gudni claims to have received.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

— Yes

Notes: The pluralism of MMS is evident at several levels: Culturally, Adepts come from several countries spanning East/West and Africa; socially, Adepts are discouraged from renouncing their previous religious beliefs; theologically, the seven Mystery Schools are distributed around the world, embedded in local traditions, and offer localized forms of transcendent wisdom that do not negate each other.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

— Yes

Notes: With the two caveats that MMS followers from different countries may have slightly different symbolic roles within MMS (such as the Japanese having a special role in bringing the coming Shambhalla) and that some religious groups, anti-cult organizations, and media are opposed to MMS. MMS leadership typically engages in behind-the-scenes legal disputes with such groups and does not publically feud.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

— No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

— Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

— No

Notes: Although members may speak of feeling misfit from birth and having supernatural experiences communicating with spirits, for example, which they associate with being groomed for future MMS membership.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

— Yes

Notes: MMS workshops emphasize the personal transformation and personal significance of Initiation, which may include changes in behavior and fashion--which exist parallel to the broader Platonic Theosophical view of Good versus Evil which permeates MMS teachings.

↳ Assigned by class:

— No

Notes: Not assigned by class, but the cost of MMS courses and the imperative to "Live Royally" may deter lower SES people. However, MMS does have a sliding payscale for participants from developing countries.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

— No

↳ Assigned by gender:

— No

Notes: Not assigned by gender, but MMS teachings in Japan broadly appeal to more women than men.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

— Yes

Notes: Formal membership entails the completion of a specified number of classes (see media file) to advance from Adept to Healer to Ritual Master 1, 2, 2.5, Guide, and 3.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

— No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

— No

Notes: Not proselytize in a traditional sense, but new Initiates are actively recruited through Guides giving free informational events or Gudni Gudnason giving free online meditation classes. There are several review videos actively promoted by MMS -- such as <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pN82HKQozwA> -- which describes a woman who found community and healing through MMS and

became a salary-earning Guide.

Does the religion have official political support

— No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

— No

Notes: Not formal apostasy, although some former members have described feeling pressured to remain within MMS and continue to purchase workshops (see <https://www.vice.com/en/article/k78ay3/inside-the-bizarre-cult-whose-members-allege-sexual-and-financial-exploitation>).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

— Estimated population, numeric: 10000

Notes: The round number of 10,000 is often cited as global MMS membership. On August 7th, 2021, MMS hosted a 'Midsummer Prophecy' (manatsu no yogen) on Zoom. The 293 participants in the event were a mix of individual Japanese people, larger gatherings of students from 63 MMS salons across Japan, and a few Koreans. The total attendance was in the ballpark of 1,000 people.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

— Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

— Yes

↳ Are they written:

— No

Notes: MMS has some written material, such as 'The Cherubim's Flames', booklet of ritual incantations and mantras written by Gudni Gudnason and used by initiates. Gudni often appeals to sacred texts, especially 'The Hermetica' (which is called the "bible" for Ritual Masters); the Bible; the Zohar, among others. However, it is more appropriate to classify MMS scriptures as primarily oral.

↳ Are they oral:

— Yes

Notes: MMS has oral scriptures in a few senses. First, scriptures (Hermetica, Thesophy and Kabbalah) are transmitted to students not primarily through their own intense self-study but through taking MMS classes/seminars--which places an emphasis on orally receiving the teachings. That is not to say that MMS initiates are not self-studying (for example, MMS sells their own compilation of the Hermetica in English and Japanese). In another sense, MMS oral scriptures are oracular speech channeled down by Third Order Masters (and possibly other high-level leadership). It is important to note that Gudni repeatedly stresses that his channeled oral pronouncements are "not core teachings" -- and he has also expressed doubt about if full trance channeling is an authentic practice (or perhaps corrupted by human ego). However, based on how such channeled and oracular pronouncements may be received as revealed, authoritative, and of particular importance to MMS followers (regardless of the caveat of not being a core teaching), it seems appropriate to etically classify such speech as oral scripture. In that sense, the most important transmission of oral scripture comes from Gudni Gudnason, the Founder of MMS, whose 'channeling contract' is with the angel Sanat Kumara. Mr. Gudnason can reveal prophecies, new teaching modules (such as Ensofic Ray), and eschatological pronouncements (such as the 2012 Armageddon or 2021 Shambhalla) through charismatic speech, often at paid MMS events but also in various social media, interviews, and podcasts. Although there's may be some confusion about the particulars, MMS followers believe (or express inconsequential agnosticism) about Gudni Gudnason's biographical account of having grown up with perhaps akinetic catatonia, spiritually unified with his dead brother in a supernatural realm; as a teenager and young man having sought out esoteric knowledge and been selected to join the Order of the Golden Dawn; having studied in the ancient Library of Alexandria (housed in the secret MMS headquarters in London) and in a remote and hidden temple in Tibet (where Moses visited in an earlier epoch), where Mr. Gudnason learned how to bend energy through martial arts techniques; as an adult in the USA, having an encounter with aliens called Nathors, who further imparted galactic knowledge of DNA Activation; and who regularly has astral contact with the Dalai Lama and other high initiates. Therefore, Mr. Gudnason's pronouncements--often delivered with rhetorical flourish, sometimes meant to be

literal and othertimes clouded in metaphor, often spoken with some degree of humor in a style approaching Tibetan Crazy Wisdom, what Trungpa Rinpoche described as 'wisdom gone wild'--constitutes a living oral scripture of sorts for MMS believers (although the terms 'oral scripture' is not emic to MMS).

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Each of the primary scriptures (Kabbalah, Hermetica and to a lesser extent, Theosophical texts) have their own accounts of the creation of scripture. Oral scriptures produced by MMS leadership rely on charisma, faith in channeling and oracular power, and the perceived authenticity of the speaker.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: Because MMS incorporates many scriptures, each scripture has its own creation narrative. For example, in the case of the Zohar, Jewish legend has it that Shimon was inspired by Prophet Elijah, after many years sequestered in a cave studying the Torah--and so some would consider the Kabbalah, or Oral Torah, to be revealed by a High God. Since Zohar is incorporated into MMS teachings, at least some scriptures are revealed by a High God.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– I don't know

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The Third Order is clear that the Core Teachings of MMS are ancient and unchanging as they are passed down through the lineage. From an etic perspective, oral scriptures more broadly may change (new teachings introduced, new interpretations of older teachings, new emphases based on changing situations, and so on) based on on revelations by Sanat Kumara to Mr. Gudnason and further transmitted to MMS followers. This broader sense of oral scripture is focused on revelations about the future; for example, the September 21st, 2021 anchoring of Shambhala on earth.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Not in the sense of an institutional literati or priestly class who professionally interpret scripture. However, many of the written manuals began in English and were translated into Japanese (translation always leads to some re-interpretation of meaning). And in Japan, Hideto Nakagome (as Third Order), the main teaching Guides at the Hatagaya Headquarters, and the monthly Guide Quorum meetings may influence shaping the tone and emphasis of Mr. Gudnason's oral teachings and their interpretations. Like other religious groups operating in multiple countries, interpretations can proliferate in new social contexts.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Guides transmit the scriptural knowledge learned in seminars. Also, Hideto Nakagome takes an active role in teaching Japanese initiates, as does Dave Lanyon in North America.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: MMS has not constructed monumental architecture; however, claims are made that some natural formations and historical monuments are connected to the Mystery School. For example, Mr. Gudnason teaches that the submerged rock formation off the coast of Yonaguni--one of the Yaeyama Islands, the most westernmost inhabited island of Japan--is the historical site of the first humans coming to earth and establishing a city of peace.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Some public spaces

Notes: Iconography is imported from dozens of religious, spiritual, and mythological sources. Although MMS does not have its own iconography, it is pervasive. Published material may have dozens of iconographic features throughout--done in the style of New Age pastiche or collage. Pentagrams, yantras, tarot images, mystical alphabets like Grimoire and Eochian, Tibetan thangkhas, crystals, laminated spiritual certifications, energetic beads, Christian crosses, Japanese ofuda, and Tibetan dorjees and phurbhas, yamabushi pilgrimage sticks, handmade sigils, kabbalistic signs, menorahs, romantic paintings of a knighting ceremonies, medieval swords and Tibetan singing bowls. Gudni Gudnason, Dave Lanyon and Hideto Nakagome (the Third Order) often wear golden ankhs (the Egyptian hieroglyphic representing the key to life); upon completing the Ritual Master program, initiates are given silver ankh necklaces. Similarly, the Third Order nearly always wear a protective ring of ancient design. And Mr. Gudnason often poses with three fingers raised, a reference to the title of 'Hermes the Thrice-Greatest' and the centrality of the Hermetica in MMS teachings.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Notes: In the main, MMS liberally borrows iconography from other spiritual groups, religions, occult and mythological sources. While none are in themselves distinct, the combination of them approaches originality among New Religious Movements and spirituality groups. Also, the Third Order wears necklaces and rings that approach distinct features for identifying the highest level of MMS leadership. And Gudni's flamboyant style and hand gestures are iconographic in the sense of indexing principles of MMS, such as Living Royally, being in Joy, Sacred Dandyism, Spiritual Beauty, the centrality of the Hermetica, among others.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Absolutely, all around the world and several in Japan (Mount Fuji, Mount Aso, Yonaguni, Kurama, as examples); along with the headquarters in Setagaya, Tokyo.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Notes: Mount Fuji, Mount Aso, Yonaguni, Kurama, Lake Biwa, and others, are sacred sites corresponding to environmental features.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Perhaps the most common axiom of MMS is: "We are Eternal Spirits. We have never been born and we can never die." Mr. Gudnason described to me how Eternal Spirit travels through the universe and is given a mission on Earth. On Earth, we receive physical bodies (what he calls a "rental vehicle") that requires the Soul ("the computer program") to operate it. There are three entities: Spirit, soul and physical body. The Spirit operates the physical body through the soul.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: There are three entities: Spirit, soul and physical body. The Spirit operates the physical body through the soul.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Notes: MMS cosmology teaches that the soul is yoked to the physical body when we get our Earth Mission. Exactly when the soul enters the picture depends on each Spirit entity. After death, the physical body decomposes in the material world while the soul and Spirit, yoked together, exit the body as an intertwined dyad and continue on for 3,000 years of additional schooling: the 4th, 5th, and 6th Dimensions (out of Seven). After 3,000 years, in the 7th Dimension, if the Spirit and soul have not already decoupled, then this process occurs in the 7th Dimension--and the soul departs. Spirit is eternal.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: However, MMS teaches a distinction. Because we are Eternal Beings, our time on earth in our specific corporeal bodies is not life distinct from an afterlife. Mr. Gudnason said in an interview that "there is no afterlife, there is just life. We are Eternal Beings. This journey down here--get a rental vehicle, drive around, leave it--it's life. There is no heaven and hell." While this distinction is important, MMS does have elaborate teachings on the afterlife and what it entails.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Although MMS teaches that there is no Heaven or Hell in a Christian sense, there are specific details about the spatio-materialistic nature of the afterlife that are based on the Hermetica. Mr. Gudnason describes how after 'death' (in quotations because he considers it a misnomer to make the distinction between life and afterlife) the dead person is shocked to discover that they retain a physical body and reside in physical space--even in the Spirit Realm. The death process involves following a light through a tunnel, in which relatives and guide you into the Great Hall. "In the Great Hall, you will meet other angels and higher entities who evaluate your level--where are you at. From that evaluation, you are separated from your relatives and your people. You will probably do some time in Kama Loka. You go somewhere, most people don't go deep into it, the 1st or 2nd level for a short time, just to adjust to the light. It's not like purgatory and burning off sin--we don't sin, we just learn [...]. Sin is a human concept [...] After Kama Loka, there is kind of a Purgatory--but not in the Christian sense--it's just a chamber in which you will be face-to-face with anybody you've ever hurt. You have the opportunity for forgiveness. After Purgatory, you go back to the Great Hall. After that, your assigned to a handler. The handler takes you up to the 4th Dimension, then 5th and 6th, spending 1,000 years in each dimension. This is when you really learn about what's going on on this planet [...] And then the 7th Dimension--and the soul and spirit separate."

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: MMS teaches that most people will spend time in Purgatory-like space called the Kama Loka. In Buddhism, Kama Loka encompasses the lower realms of demons, ghosts, animals and humans and is represented in the Tibetan 'Wheel of Life' (Bhāvachakra) as spatially lowest/below.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: MMS teachings are complicated on the matter of reincarnation. Mr. Cudnason, both in private conversation and in public addresses, describes how he disagreed with the Dalai Lama on the matter of reincarnation during a private meeting they shared in Linköping in 1987. On the one hand, MMS teaches that reincarnation is a coercive dogma that enslaves people to their negative realities in this world because they are hoping for riches in their next life. Because we are Eternal Beings, we were never born, cannot die, and are not reincarnated into another physical body. However, there is an MMS teaching of 'reincarnation' that distinguishes itself from Hindu-Buddhist notions in several ways and more commonly called 'emanations.'

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: But again, an important caveat. The previous you who performed karmic actions was not you, but rather a related substance within your Boddhisattva/cloud. However, previous incarnations of that Boddhisattva on earth may lead to karmic consequences for the next emanation. It is not clear the extent to which this is taught in MMS--or how well it is generally understood among followers, who may bring into MMS pre-existing religious and cultural commitments to reincarnation and karma.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Generally no, although the Mystery School does have specific rituals for corpses--which have been performed in limited circumstances.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Although there are MMS death rituals, the deceased person's relatives will determine burial rituals and style based on their own cultural and religious norms.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic

activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: In emic MMS speech and teachings, the idea of a singular High God is downplayed, in part because of the extremely diverse array of gods and spirits (described as 'infinite') that populate the MMS cosmology. With that important caveat, from an etic perspective En-Sof sits atop all other deities, spirits and angels. En-Sof is the non-existential aspect of God (versus the existential part) in Kabbalah. It is called the Source. MMS teaches four levels of Godhood: En-Sof (The Source), Elohim (who alone judges humans), Saviors (Jesus for Christians, Muhammad for Muslims, and other prophets/saviors depending on the beliefs of the initiate; inclusive recognition of saviors allows MMS to reach a broader audience); and Thyself (your Realized Eternal Self). En-sof may be considered a High God—in other contexts, and among different cohorts of followers, the full Godhead may be experienced as a High God (since it sits atop a cosmology of other deities, angels, and spirits). As described by Mr. Cudnason, En-Sof sacrificed space within itself to allow humans to enter and have self-realization. Because humans entered into En-Sof, we humans are En-Sof and are thus Supreme Beings. Because humans and En-sof are of analogous substance, MMS puts a heavy emphasis on humans—as you—as the highest god. This may be appealing to MMS initiates who are seeking self-transformation, individuality, and an enlarged sense of self (as described by scholarship on Japanese spiritual therapies). As Mr. Cudnason put it: "We are the highest God, because it's all about me. You have to learn that it's all about me; I'm here and it's all about me. And each individual has to think that way. I am the highest god. The Self—the Realized Self as Spirit. We are only different because of our individuality. And you can only see these differences because of our personalities. But in the spirit form, when we are together in the Cloud of Intelligence, we have one mind and think the same thing."

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: MMS teaches that En-Sof (and the entire Hierarchy of Light) is omniscient. Humans sign a contract about our mission on Earth. Supernatural forces cannot alter the substance of that contract through interventions in the Earth. As described by Mr. Gudnason: "This whole world history has been decided way before we came here. There's a contract for it, it's signed and done, no changes. We're just living something we already decided on. There's no free will except the choice between good and evil. Everything else is predetermined."

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Because of the pre-ordained contract that determines human history.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The contract that humans sign with En-Sof before entering Earth determines everything that will follow. This act deliberately shapes casual efficacy. However, MMS teachings follow the Kabbalah in that En-Sof is beyond rewards and punishments, beyond human affairs, but rather is itself all of humanity and our experiences within its essence.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– No

Notes: All things come from En-Sof and are En-Sof. However, our earthly rewards come our behavior and karma.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– No

Notes: Elohim is the only deity who is allowed to judge humans. He judges our thoughts, words and actions. This judgement determines where we go in Kama Loka. This is not the same as conventional Christian ideas about punishment of sin in eternal Damnation. Conversely, humans are "rewarded" by good karma by spending less time (or not entering as deeply) into Kama

Loka. Mr. Gudnason teaches that Elohim is not a judgment God in the traditional Judeo-Christian sense. "Elohim does not judge you, per se. If you do something, if you're mean to a fellow human, when you go pass over, because we don't believe in death, we never die, but when you pass over, you go to purgatory, which is literally, I have been there, I know it, it's a chamber the size of this room, and in this chamber, you spend time face-to-face with everybody you know. You may have forgotten it—there are people we've hurt without knowing it. They will be in our face and we will understand. We will have regret in our heart and ask for forgiveness and come to that point. Everything that happens after we cross over is done so that we are able to return to the Light."

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
— Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
— No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
— No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
— No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
— Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
— Yes [specify]: Because humans are a part of En-Sof, our Realized Self reflects the High God--and as such MMS teaches and practices to "Be Royal" physically and materially to reflect our inherent divinity.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
— No
Notes: Humans cannot communicate with En-sof, and has similar features to Hindu conceptions of Nirguna (a 'distinctionless' High God).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
— Yes

Notes: Human spirits come in two forms: un-incarnated and incarnated. Un-incarnated human spirits (meaning having 'died' but not been reincarnated yet) act as spirit guides to those on earth or serve in some capacity with the Hierarchy of Light. In some instances, un-incarnated human spirits can become ghosts and linger in the world and cause harm (and must be removed through exorcism). Another type of un-incarnated spirits are those who never had a physical body. They are 'on the way' to Earth to get a physical body. They also serve as spirit guides and are part of our daily lives but are not manifest in a material sense. MMS psychics can interact with them and seek advice from them but there is a limitation to that interaction because un-incarnated beings do not understand human senses and emotions since they lack a human body. Incarnate beings are all humans who die physical 'death' (there is no death strictly speaking in MMS teachings). We then begin a journey back to earth, receive a physical body and soul (soul existing before this process began), and are born on Earth as part of our mission throughout eternity. MMS teaches that incarnated spirits are both physical and non-physical, with a soul that floats away from the body at death and does 3,000 years of 'after-life-school.' Humans who seek out higher learning in esoteric knowledge can shortcut the 3,000 year 'after-life-school' and can achieve a faster evolution. MMS "reincarnation" does not entail multiple physical bodies, but rather "emanations" whereby each spirit (on their way to Earth to receive their first physical body/life) acts as a Spirit Guide to others who are already incarnate. There is only one physical life in a body. After, humans "die" a physical death and our intertwined spirit and soul journey upwards to begin 3,000 years of spiritual education in the 4th, 5th and 6th dimensions. MMS teaches that our soul/spirit does not come back to Earth to receive another body in the sense of transmigration of the soul. There is also an inner MMS teaching about lineage teachers being part of a Boddhisatva, as told about in Tibet by high lamas. Being born as part of a Boddhisatva is not something that can be predicted or caused, it just happens to some people.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:
— Yes

Notes: Mr. Gudnason speaks publicly about his unique birth, which involves being born alongside a twin brother who died thereafter. Consequently, Mr. Gudnason "had no veil and everything was wide open and I could see everything." He teaches that supernatural beings "are around us all the time; some even live here." These take human and non-human form (oftentimes with little distinction between the two).

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Mr. Gudnason describes interacting and feeling a multitude of spirits, as do many MMS followers. Human spirits are nearly always positive (they can guide and be felt by living humans, they can offer suggestions) and very rarely can become negative (in the case of poltergeist, for example).
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes

Notes: There is an important caveat. While MMS teachings include the '12 Races of Earth' (derived from Theosophical work on 'Root Races')—which for MMS includes vampires, trolls, elves, mermaids, among others—these 'races' are taught to be material beings. They may be able to do seemingly supernatural things (like vampires can fly), but in fact they are terrestrial. Past these '12 Races', however, there's a separately-classed infinite number of supernatural beings in the Hierarchy of Light who act in the world. More broadly, MMS teachings include a huge diversity of galactic beings, alien races and supernatural forces. There are also immaterial beings who inhabit the lower three of seven broadly-defined spiritual dimensions. These lower spiritual dimensions above Earth's density are both spiritual and physical and correlate with J.R.R. Tolkien's writings about 'Middle Earth.' The 4th, 5th, and 6th spiritual dimensions, also called the Schools of Spirit, exist above the first three spiritual dimensions. It is in these dimensions that human souls go after physical death in a purgatory-like process prior to entering the schools of spirit described earlier.
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– No

Notes: Although Jesus Christ is a part of MMS teachings and he is considered both human and divine while incarnate.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

Notes: According to the cosmology of MMS, there are basically unlimited spiritual beings. There are thousands of specific archangels for the functioning of universal laws. Angelic hosts are taught to be infinite. Following Theosophical texts about Ascendent Masters/Mahatmas, MMS teaches that some progressed/physically deceased souls—called Masters of Light—become teachers for helping humans evolve higher consciousness. They have different specializations. The more ancient Masters of Light are celestial intelligences who came to Earth millions of years ago to facilitate various energetic plans of Elohim for the evolution of humanity and Earth.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– Yes
Notes: The cosmology is arranged by hierarchy but MMS teachings stresses not so much a ranking system but different supernatural beings having different roles and attributes.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Although MMS is not characterized by codified moral edicts and ethical norms for initiates, one could say that there is a degree of supernatural monitoring. This role is specifically assigned to Elohim, who plays a role in watching us while alive and judging us when we pass over (you cannot 'die' in a conventional sense in MMS). To quote an interview with Mr. Gudnason: "For us, Elohim is a little bit like Odin. He has the Watchers, the pair of ravens Huginn and Muninn, they go out. And there's a race on the planet that are called Watchers; they are part of the 12 Races. They are connected to Elohim."

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

Notes: However, vegetarianism is encouraged and sometimes required of initiates during certain events and courses of study. Meat is taught to lower one's energy, along with drugs and alcohol and spicy food.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– No

Notes: There are not taboos around sacred space. However, creating sacred spaces (called Temples) through sacred geometry and gridding is central to MMS. The main headquarters in Hatagaya (Tokyo) is a permanently sealed Temple because of the gridding work done on it, along with the power of the stone (hokutolite) in the back of the room. Initiates are trained to constantly be making sacred spaces in rooms they enter.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Ritual Masters use Tibetan phurbas in various rituals, and are instructed to not let anyone else touch their personalized phurba. This is the same with the DNA Activation wand for Healers. Most initiates are sensitive about this taboo and it is generally enforced in daily life.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Incest:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Laziness is especially bad in several senses. Mr. Gudnason teaches that "We're not in the Mystery School on vacation. We're not here on this planet on vacation. We have a mission." In that sense, initiates are sometimes called 'Light Workers' who are working to raise the vibration to humanity to create Shambhala. In Japan, learning various spiritual activations in seminars are framed as forms of 'work' (wāku) by the teaching Guides. Completing seminars and spiritual activations often lead to acknowledging each other's hard work (otsukaresama) and a sense of completion among participants. In another sense, MMS leadership gives recognition to top performing Guides (who initiate the most Adepts) and various forms of encouragement to inactive Guides. Because Guides and Healers can earn money for themselves and the MMS headquarters, working hard has both a financial and spiritual aspect. Healers work hard at healing; Warriors of Light and Ritual Masters work hard--spiritually and physically--to protect humanity from malign spirits.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
 - Notes: However, Mr. Gudnason said that: "If you don't do rituals, that's bad. You can do them wrong if the intention is good." MMS classes often teach how to properly do rituals, empowerments, and activations. Several helping Guides often walk around the room and may correct initiates if they are off on ritual performance.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
 - Notes: 1st-, 2nd- and 3rd-step Initiates all have different degrees of ritual work they should do in the morning and evening. It is especially important to do morning ritual work (centered on the creation of a magic circle) to ensure protection and that the day goes off well.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Overall

Notes: Overall, supernatural beings care for humans in every way, although the beings are so widely classified (they are infinite and so in a sense beyond classification) that it is reductive to mention specific forms of care from specific supernatural beings.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: However, there is a central place for saviors, drawn from all religious traditions, in MMS cosmology. While saviors have an important role, overall messianic beliefs (as practiced in the monotheistic book religions, for example) are not emphasized. In the sense of popular practice, some MMS initiates may look to Mr. Gudnason—the Third Order Founder with a biography of being initiated into an ancient secret lineage and being the key person to bring this lineage into the wider public (through taking seminars)—as restoring and maintaining a spiritual tradition through which humanity can be saved and a future utopia (Shambhala) can be ushered in. It is important to note that initiates do not use the language of messiah or talk about Mr. Gudnason and that he sometimes downplays his role in trying to save humanity. However, there are several seminars that teach how Mr. Gudnason has compromised his health on several occasions in order to usher in new spiritual teachings from galactic beings. At times, the emphasis on personal sacrifice for the good of humanity has messianic undertones.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: After 1,000 Hebraic years, which may not correspond with human years.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Notes: After 1,000 Hebraic years (beginning from the anchoring of Shambhala on earth on

September 21, 2021).

- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - No
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Elohim has not yet revealed to Mr. Gudnason the details of the next mission. What is clear is that humans will be done with earth and go on to their mission. Mr. Gudanson described this next mission as also temporally bounded.
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In 1,000 Hebraic years, at the world's end, everyone will exit the earth and survive into the eschaton. It is not described as only an elect few.
 - ↳ Other survival condition:
 - No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

- Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

- Yes

- ↳ What is the nature of this distinction:
 - Present (but not emphasized)
- ↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
 - Yes
- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes

Notes: MMS teachings emphasize the need for service and being "humanitarians of the heart." MMS claims to have done several charitable projects, including HIV education in South Africa, therapy for extreme introverts (hikkikomori) in Japan, donations to victims after 3/11 in the Tohoku region, and cleansing the waters of Lake Biwa. The 2014 'Sacred Planet' event advertised a 1,400 yen donation per ticket bought to the 'Philippine typhoon affected area.' <https://mmsjapan.jp/sacred-planet/2014> The idea of "no more secrets" -- allowing anyone to purchase MMS teachings -- is viewed by MMS leadership as a kind of humanitarian and democratizing deed. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NudK1jdqYeY>

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes

- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
– Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– Yes
 - Notes: Mr. Gudnason often teaches non-conformity and individual expression. One's creative freedoms are tied to the recognition that we are all Eternal Beings, sharing the same essence, but having unique earthly personalities and capabilities. Discovering one's creative side in MMS is both tied into Guide branding and a way for Adepts and lower initiates, especially in Japan, who may be feeling like misfits to find a sense of belonging.
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes
 - Notes: Mr. Gudnason often teaches the importance of not being victimized or wallowing in social sympathy. 'Living Royally' means being assertive in one's tastes and preferences, having the confidence to cultivate individual expressions, and harnessing MMS teachings to have the initiative and alchemical tools to recognize the divinity of the Self.
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– No
 - Notes: As a spiritual business, all Guides and Healers need to self-brand and emphasize their unique attributes in order to attract clients. While one Japanese Guide I interviewed has aspects of humility as central to her brand, the majority of Japanese MMS initiates are not concerned about humility and are actively rejecting modesty as they discover their royal selfhood. Likewise, the Third Order does not often embody humility in how they speak about their biographical and spiritual accomplishments, the humanity-saving goals of MMS teachings, and the personal betterment of initiates. This rejection of modesty takes on particular importance in Japan, where modesty (kenkyo) may be more socially valued than in the West. Jordan Bain, a MMS Guide in Boston, described how in the West there is more emphasis put on humility through service because of the Western tendency to over-identify with the individual self; whereas in Japan, because of different cultural norms, overcoming humility is often stressed.
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

- Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Since its inception, RMMS and later MMS teaches the central importance of the coming Shambhala. This is a future of peace and is a fundamentally optimistic attitude about the future of humanity.
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Beauty is among the most stressed virtues in MMS. It is called TIPHARETH and is the 6th Sephira on the Tree of Life. The associated phrase is: "In all things great and small, I see the beauty of the Divine Expression." Beauty is emphasized at every level of social organization and spiritual teaching: 1st-step Initiates (during Adept training) are taught that they come from En-Sof and are themselves Gods and Goddesses; to nurture their Eternal Spirit, they should Live Royally; and through alchemical processes, recognition of true inner self transforms and beautifies the outer body. Within MMS, individual Guides and leaders are self-branded as beautiful, especially Eiko Gudnason (beauty alchemist) and Mailove (sensual magician and spiritual beauty body). Mr. Gudnason expresses his joy through high fashion--what is branded as Sacred Dandyism. All MMS Guides are instructed to materially and physically upgrade to reflect their Eternal Spirit, and the fashion policy at MMS Headquarters (not strictly enforced but present) is for female Guides to wear dresses and skirts and not pants. It is common for Initiates to go through physical transformations from 'normal' Japanese fashion to more individualized attire that projects more sensuality or wealth. Within the Ritual Master syllabus is a Beauty Council and several elective courses are offered, on the way to becoming a Guide, which are explicitly about beauty (such as 'Cleopatra's Beauty Secrets: Alchemy for Transformational Beauty'). In MMS, beauty is a realization of True Self, a lifestyle that matches your physical reality with this inner realization, an aesthetic which pervades clothing fashion, interior design, and ritual objects, a form of self-branding for specific Guides/leaders to individualize and gain a niche market of potential Adepts, and a general marketing technique of the school to project an image of popularity with beautiful, successful and famous people. See: <https://www.modernmysteryschoolint.com/2018/08/20/transformational-alchemy-cleopatra-beauty-secrets/>
fbclid=IwAR1FbZw2Z_cukBWBHBR0LSJPxd09gAQazg235_hN78eWV0c7HVkn16x9a8U
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: Healing
 - Notes: In MMS teaching, the world is sick and DNA Activation and the MMS lineage is focused on healing and restoration of health. For example, while teaching about the Kabbalistic Tree of Life (Sefirot), Mr. Gudnason explained how Malkuth (the lowest part of the tree), is commonly misunderstood to be Earth. In this passage, he reiterates the central optimism about the coming Shambhala, the need for MMS initiates to do the work to bring it into existence, and the importance of healing in MMS. "Malkuth, this part of the tree, in most teachings is the earth we live in. That's not true. That earth we are supposed to create if we follow the create path according to the right vibration, that should Shambhala, the world of peace, New Jerusalem. That should be a world where there is no hunger, no suffering, no weapons, no need for armies or soldiers or any of it. It should be a peaceful good world without pain and suffering. But it is not so therefore we are on a healing path. Our world is on a healing path.

The people need healing. Healing means we need to get back to that one vibration so that we can together create that world. We cannot do that solo. We can have a pretty good life solo, but in the end, it is a communal thing, it's a community, we all have to become one."

—Yes [specify]: Self-Transformation

Notes: Most MMS teachings circle back to the recognition of our true selves as eternal Galactic beings. Recognizing this opens up many avenues of self-transformation through awakening our royal and godly natures. Meditations and activations help initiates to love themselves, find their true identity, overcome social pressure to conformity, and take joy in expressing their divine selves. This can lead to transformations of the self spiritually (increased awareness, capacities and responsibilities), materially (upgrades in dress, interior design, posture and consumerism) and socially (quitting jobs and changing relationships, among other things). For example, at the end of the Know Thyself seminar in October 2021 at the MMS headquarters in Hatagaya (Tokyo), one of the primary teaching Guides posted on Facebook that: "The transformation (henyou) of the participants was amazing. All the instructors were very impressed."

—Yes [specify]: Continuity

Notes: The concept of 'lineage' is central to MMS teachings. Mr. Gudnason locates himself as the current teacher in a lineage that extends back to Adam, Noah and King Salomon, and more recently includes British Occultists, Theosophers, and grandmasters of Knights Templars. In Japan, the MMS lineage is a key attraction for some Japanese followers who are seeking out community, belonging, and larger purpose (ikigai). Many MMS teachings and marketing materials emphasize lineage and the importance of continuity of esoteric teachings. For a list of the people in the MMS lineage: <https://www.modernmysteryschoolint.com/2009/06/27/lineage-of-the-mms/> Mr. Gudnason explaining the importance of 'lineage' and the initiatory path of MMS: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vgbTfj5T238> A clear description of how lineage and continuity functions in MMS: <https://modernmysteryschooluk.com/lineage/>

—Yes [specify]: Joy

Notes: In a 2008 seminar, Mr. Gudnason explained that the alchemical, hermetic, kabbalistic Philosopher's Stone is actually Joy. "It's the most important thing on the planet," he said. Living in one's joy is a process advocated within MMS teachings whereby an initiate discovers the eternal nature of self and corresponding sources of individualistic joy. In an interview, Mr. Gudnason explained to me how materialism is part of joy. "Focus on the material because we are here [in the material world]. Having fun, living life, being in joy. I enjoy putting on my bowtie, my clothes, taking my car down to the mall and walking around having people see me." This idea of 'being in joy' is somewhat synonymous with 'being royal' in MMS teachings. It is also tied to creativity; for example, in the teaching that Leonardo da Vinci (who is believed to be a Mystery Schol initiate) lived in constant 'joy states' which increased his creativity. Also, joy is central to descriptions of the coming Shambhala on earth. "We have to be proper. We have to be a certain way to fit in. And they break that mold. [...] The key to joy...they are silly. When we are silly, we are happy. But we can't be silly, right, we have to be proper. Bullshit! Let's be silly. [...] I've learned that my best quality is my willingness to humiliate myself. If we get to that point, we're in joy. Life becomes joy. Everything becomes joy."

—Yes [specify]: Awareness

Notes: When I asked Mr. Gudnason about centrally important virtues in MMS, he stressed awareness. The Third Order does not think of themselves as a collective of teachers. They awaken and bring out the divinity in initiates that they initiates already possess but lack awareness to recognize. The root of the problem is consciousness, which grounds you in the physical reality and takes you away from God states. Awareness is the key to this divinity. Accordingly, many teachings focus on increasing awareness of divinity through channeling, activations, and increasing sensitivity to energy, auras and chakras. MMS teachings can operate at multiple levels simultaneously, at once stressing the baseness of consciousness/materialism and yet tacitly celebrating the material transformations of initiates (in Japan, especially towards fashion, consumer, and social individualism).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

— No

Notes: However, Mr. Gudnason described a 9-year period of celibacy and noted that a future Third Order person might also need to go through a period of celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

— No

Notes: The group is generally sex positive and has non-binary and LGBTQ+ members.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

— No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, fasting is not required for initiates (there is an exception for 3rd-Step Ritual Master training).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Although not widely practiced, there are teachings within MMS that caution against eating overly-spicy foods, alcohol and meat. In Japan, eating meat and drinking alcohol is so central to personal and work life that these teachings are taken as heuristic. In some ways, the way that MMS teaches about food taboos has elements of Hindu philosophy about the qualities (guna) of food--and cautions against some tamas and rajas foods.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: I define 'sacrifice of valuable property' in the most prosaic way of meaning money. In that sense, the MMS syllabus requires initiates to pay set fees to increase their Light and spiritual knowledge as they progress along the Path. This is not a singular Path (there are different options and courses, and initiates express different objectives). But the principle of 'equal exchange' mandates that initiates pay for progression. As a researcher, I took several seminars; however, as I was invited by Mr. Gudnason and did not pay, I did not receive the secret initiations and did not receive spiritual energy transfer. It is in this sense that membership requires sacrifice of money.

↳ To out-groups:

– No

Notes: Because of the model of MMS, initiates pay money to other initiates, who act as Guides and Healers; and eventually move on to taking seminars at the headquarters. In both cases, money remains within MMS. It is not paid to out-groups.

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Membership is predicated on having taking step-by-step initiation. Each step requires a period

of time. Even after finishing every possible seminar (which is rarely done), Healers and Guides must take yearly recertification classes.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

— No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

— Yes

Notes: Below is a description written by Dave Lanyon of MMS's ethical precepts and beliefs. We believe that all humans have come from a Divine Origin and are therefore made from a Divine substance, therefore in a sense are Gods and Goddesses! We believe that all humans are Eternal, that we have never been born and therefore we can never die. Yes, we have a physical body, but so does the butterfly have a shell, a larva that then transforms into their true nature. We believe that we are in that process, becoming our true self! We believe that all humans have all the knowledge we need, and that whatever questions we have, the answers reside within ourselves. The Mystery School was established only to assist humans to find those answers, not to give them! We believe that humans are constructed by three components, physical body, soul and spirit and that all three of these need to be taken care of through wisdom, nurturing, and healing. The Mystery School Lineage provides this with ancient metaphysical tools used and perfected over thousands of years. The Lineage has focused on working with and creating tools to handle the complicated machine or the computer of the human vehicle, what we call the MIND. Our tools are aimed to help each individual take back control of this vehicle for themselves so they can create a better life. We believe that all of our physical manifestations start within the mind thus it is so important to take good care of it! We believe that humans are born as two different genders, male and female, as so proven by biology and that the science of this is accurate. We then believe in the individual's freedom to regard themselves as whatever or whoever makes them happy, but that the facts are indisputable that our foundational physicality is that we are all born either male or female and that there are undeniable differences in that foundation. We furthermore believe that we have certain archetypes for us to follow and strive to be like, these all being Gods and Goddesses of ancient times on earth, bringing us good values and traits for us to follow and admire. These archetypes have inspired us humans for thousands of years and they define our lives in every way, allowing us to overcome any obstacle that comes before us, to grow greater than our previous self and rise victorious in life. Without these divine archetypes we would not nor could we attain such heights of human potential. We believe in the essential goodness of all humans or their capacity for such, even though history may show different. Humans are innately good, and with the correct environmental influence and inner self work we can accomplish our highest human potential to do good! We believe in the right of self-determination as well as taking full responsibility for one's own thoughts, actions and words in all situations. We believe that the true ownership of those things is laid at the feet of the individual self, whether it bears good or bad fruit for themselves or others. We believe that the character and integrity of a individual is far more important and meaningful than the identification of one by a group or a collective. We believe people should have the freedom to express themselves in a healthy way, unburdened by any constraint to conform to a particular group or person's personal opinions or acceptance of those views. We believe in the power of humans to create a better world and that with the correct nurturing we can accomplish that goal. This would not be accomplished with any one organization (including the Modern Mystery School), religion or otherwise such, but rather through the power of the people themselves, led by their love of freedom, acceptance of themselves and others and peace! MODERN MYSTERY SCHOOL CORE VALUES We value life as we know it, that sacred spark from the universe that can and will ignite the world to become a better place for us all. We value every individual, no matter who or what they are, by what name they go or ideas they have. We will do our best to make certain that they can express themselves in the most healthy and positive way possible for humans. We value that, after the awakening of the inner being, there is a need for self-expression of their soul, their inner feelings and thoughts. We welcome that expression and see it as a part of our organization, as a part of who and what we are. We value being different, we see it as being unique. We welcome those who suffer from the ignorance and judgement of others who do not understand nor accept that uniqueness. We value society, as it has given us the opportunity to serve the greater good to a larger audience. We value Governments of countries who try to do their best to take care of their citizens. We value those who want to create a positive change in the world and we gladly support their efforts.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

— Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

— Yes

Notes: At every level of initiation are matching personal rituals that are highly encouraged to be performed on a daily basis.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

— I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

— Yes

Notes: There are several group rituals and activations that are required at even step of initiation.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– Yes
Notes: Yearly recertifications for Guides and Healers are designed as orthodoxy/orthopraxy checks. During these day-long seminars, initiates demonstrate their knowledge of various rituals (both for personal use and for clients) and any mistakes are corrected.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Yes
Notes: Yearly recertifications for Guides and Healers are designed as orthodoxy/orthopraxy checks. During these day-long seminars, initiates demonstrate their knowledge of various rituals (both for personal use and for clients) and any mistakes are corrected.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: Not in the sense of certain tribal religions. However, MMS initiates (at least in Japan) often individualize in appearance and may wear certain jewelry that identifies them as MMS members.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: At least in Japan, initiates do not often use fictive kin terms.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
– Yes
Notes: Mr. Gudnason often uses the language of Brothers and Sisters in emails sent out the MMS base.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A lineage.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: MMS has assisted in disaster relief after the 3/11 Tohoku disaster, to poverty and HIV relief in South Africa, and to the Phillipines after the 2013 Super Typhoon Yolanda. I do not see internal institutional documents which corroborate this charity. However, there are websites that show pictures of MMS people giving assistance or raising money for assistance.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: I'm not sure 'bureaucracy' is the best word, but a hallmark aspect of MMS is that initiates interact with levels of administration (and can eventually become the administration themselves).

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: However, MMS performed rituals over Lake Biwa with the intention of cleansing it of pollution.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Not in a traditional sense of like a Christian 10% tithe or a Bavarian 8% church tax bill. But initiates must pay for courses and to remain active within MMS.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Because MMS is a spiritual business in Japan, not a government-recognized religious group (shukyo hojin), claimed income through seminars is taxable.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: MMS initiates might include members of the military.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: However, the combination of several ancient and magical languages is potentially distinctive of MMS. This can include Enochian, Sanskrit, Runes, Futhark and Malachim.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Initiates use languages based on their socialization in different countries.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Not a formal calendar that is unique to MMS. But the Wicca calendar is used and rituals are performed on the equinoxes.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: There are some events when food is provided or can be purchased.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

–Other [specify in comments]